

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2591662>

THE INFLUENCE OF DISTRIBUTION CHANNEL UPON CREDIT SERVICE ADOPTION: CASE STUDY OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN THAILAND

Palida Srisornkompon

Faculty of Business Administration, Panyapiwat Institution of Management, Thailand
Email: palidasri@pim.ac.th

Received: 2019-02-26

Accepted: 2019-03-07

Published online: 2019-03-12

Abstract

The objectives of this study are to 1) study the opinion on distribution channel and decision making on credit service adoption of small and medium enterprises, and 2) study the effect of distribution channel on credit service adoption. The data were collected from 165 small sized enterprises and 235 medium sized enterprises in Thailand. Hypothesis was tested by AMOS to conform Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The results indicated that small enterprises used excessive offline channel for credit adoption with coefficient of determination at 75.7 percent (R square = 0.757). Similar to medium enterprises, the research indicates that medium enterprises adopted offline channel for credit service with coefficient of determination at 90.3 percent (R square = 0.903). The finding could be concluded that medium enterprises represented higher satisfaction on offline channel rather than small enterprises.

Keywords: Small enterprises, medium enterprises, distribution channel, credit service.

1. Introduction

Money demonstrates the influence factor that is very important not less than other social and business affecting factors. Both individual and business seek for source of fund to operate their own objectives. Especially, business usually needs the money for liquidity, investment, and extension which requires more money than usual. Therefore, business will take on loan in case of not enough money and try to access the source of fund at cheaper cost. Currently, financial institutions in Thailand are 22 commercial banks (under supervision of bank of Thailand) and 15 foreign banks (Bank of Thailand, 2559). Based on number of branches, the top 5 banks rely on Bangkok Bank, Krung Thai Bank, Kasikorn Bank, Siam Commercial Bank, and Bank of Ayudhya.

The biggest banks in Thailand provide credit and investment service. In case of credit application process, Peter & Olson (2010) have suggested 3 periods of consumer behavior process for credit application as follows: 1) data searching period, 2) service contact period, and 3) after contract period. The activities stated in each period were determined and adjusted for suitable explanation of credit application process.

Nowadays, consumers have received in various forms and channels of communication resulting in revolution of adoptive behavior, credit service process and other service processes. Banking institutes have to adjust themselves to correspond with volatile changes particularly, distribution channel. In the past, banking institutes have provided distribution channel through its branch. When time has passed, bank has developed its technology and distribution channel to reach the customers, sell product and service through the branch, agent, website, and call center (called multi-channel). The management of each unit still had its activities separately and lack of information and product linkage among unit. The customer contacted one channel would obtain the product and service and pay the payment with only that channel. Recently, bank has tried to merge all information and processes in every channel. The customer can search for the information of bank's product and service, deal the contract and make the payment in any channel (called omni-channel). This concept will provide good experience to the customers (Verhoef, Kannan, & Inman, 2015) and generate higher sales to the bank eventually.

Therefore, each channel will progress its management and operation and lead to compete internally (bangkokbiznews, 2015). Due to distribution channel strategy, bank can provide optional channels to the customers such as website, telephone, branch and etc., which serves to customer satisfaction (Caruana, 2002). Customers feel that they can choose the channel by their own decision, which is quite different from the traditional channel (Rangaswamy & Bruggen, 2005). Since bank provides optional channels to the customers, researchers were interested to study the distribution channel, online and offline, affecting credit service adoption of commercial bank in Thailand by concerning of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The findings will contribute to determine channel strategy in banking industry and apply directly to credit service management to suitably serve SMEs which is indicated as an important sector of Thailand's economy (Jatusripitak, 2018)

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis

2.1 Theory of offline and online channels

Business could provide various distribution channels so that the customers can select the most convenient. Channels for them including store, online, telephone and television which could be combined together to deliver product and service. However, management and operation of each channel has been definitely separated and resulted in competition within organization. Rangaswamy & Bruggen (2005) explained that service providers provided various distribution channels; hence, the customers would feel that they have alternatives and satisfy with the business eventually. Techtargat (2014) referred channel marketing to the practice by which companies interacted with customers via multiple channels, both offline and online, in order to sell them goods and services. Companies used offline channels, which proactively reached the customer, such as physical stores, catalogs or direct mail or online channels in which

they pushed content via websites or social media, also known as inbound marketing. Other means of reaching customers with multichannel marketing included via mobile devices, text messaging, email, company website, social media, search engine optimization (SEO) or global positioning system (GPS) to track customers' proximity to goods and services. Multichannel marketing combined the practices of online and offline marketing with the goal of reaching customers on the channel that they chose. The marketers would try to use low-cost channels such as the internet. The benefits of multi-channel marketing could create challenges in marketing operations and access to customers according to their desired channel. (Harma & Mehrotra 2007) Multi-channel marketing has been activated, whereas traditional channels have been reducing their roles. All channels, both traditional channels and emerging channels such as online channel, have been adjusted to suit with the current market situation. Marketer needed to concern on balance between both channels in order to cause efficiency and effectiveness. Currently, another meaning of multi-channel marketing was consumer movement through online and offline channels that happening for different products in each type of business. The consumers were using for different channels and procedures in the process of buying products and services. Customers often used various channels in parallel and frequently switch between channels. (Van Dijk, Minocha, & Laing, 2007)

2.2 Service decision

Kotler (2006) illustrated that the fundamental psychology of comprehension in service decision was understanding the process of service decision initially. Kotler also suggested the model of five steps for service decision including problem recognition, data searching, evaluating alternatives, selection stage, and after selection behavior. Practically, customers do not need to follow step by step. They can skip some and take the steps that bring him to obtain the service. Sirimongkol, (2011) argued that the decision consisted of 5 steps beginning with need realization, data searching, evaluating alternatives, buying decision, and behavior after sales. The decision resulted from inductive and deductive thinking would cause new continuous decision. In some situations, people made decision from their belief based on their culture and past experience (Tantibunthaweevat & Maneesri, 2011). Schiffman & Kanuk (2007) indicated that consumer's decision process was the procedure of product selection between at least 2 options. Moreover, emotion, psychology and physical behavior have been involved during the decision process. Buying was activities in consumer's mind occurring during specific period of time. These activities created buying behavior including behavior of following other people. Angella & Johnson (2016) explained that consumer's buying decision process was the process before buying product and service. Business need to understand the whole process so that it can assemble marketing strategy following that process. Ratanasuwan & Srijanya (2012) suggested that consumer's buying decision consisted of need recognition, information searching to compare quality and price, and finally evaluating the alternatives and selecting the

product. Distribution channel was crucial marketing factor leading to buying decision. The channel involving all the processes of delivering the product and service to consumer. Kotler & Keller (2009) determined the pathway to transfer the product from producer to consumer within distribution channel system including producer, intermediary and consumer both business and individual. In banking system, the channel serves as service and information transfer. Bank need to form appropriated distribution channel strategy both direct and indirect to build up its competitive advantage. From literature review, therefore, researcher has selected the channel distribution's variables to determine the hypothesis for small and medium enterprises in order to investigate the appropriateness of channel distribution as follows:

H1: Offline channel influence credit service adoption by small and medium enterprises

H2: Offline along with online channel influence credit service adoption by small and medium enterprises

H3: Online channel influence credit service adoption by small and medium enterprises

2.3 Research conceptual framework

Researcher has determined the symbol of variables in conceptual framework as follows:

1. Offline channels: variables including offline allowing quickness in the process (OFF1), offline allowing accessibility for the consumer (OFF2), offline allowing credible and accurate information (OFF3), enough branch and offline channel along with call center system (OFF4), and offline channel allowing convenience to consumer including parking lot (OFF5).

2. Offline along with online channels: variables including offline along with online providing quickness (ONOFF1), Offline along with online providing information accuracy and precision (ONOFF2), offline along with online providing data, rule and procedure searching (ONOFF3), offline along with online providing enough information for service (ONOFF4), and offline along with online providing data accessibility and understanding service guideline (ONOFF5).

3. Online channels: variables including online providing quick data searching (ON1), online providing accuracy and precision in data searching (ON2), online providing convenient and quick service (ON3), online providing data, rule and procedure searching (ON4), and online providing accessible and convenient channels for credit application (ON5).

4. Service adoption decision: variables including availability of service process (Decision1), quickness within the process of credit application (Decision 2), and standard of bank’s security (Decision 3).

Symbols and variables have been indicated in this study consisted of latent variables and observable variables. Researcher has constructed the SEM as conceptual framework in figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of Research

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Population

Population in this research was retained small (business that has no more than 15 employees and permanent assets no more than 30 million baht) and medium (business that has 16-30 employees and permanent assets between 31-60 million baht) enterprises (Revenue Department, 2016).

3.2 Sample

Sample used in this research was divided into 2 groups: 1) 235 small enterprises (n=235), and 2) 165 medium enterprises (n=165). Researcher has indicated the 400 sample size by the statistics analysis technique of structural equation modeling (SEM) which was appropriate number of sample to analysis with AMOS program (Kock & Hadaya, 2018).

3.3 Research instrument

The study used survey questionnaire with interpreting meaning and level of important by Likert scale of 5 levels. 1.00-1.80 means the least preference of using the channel. 1.81-2.60 means the less preference of using the channel. 2.61-3.40 means the medium preference of using the channel. 3.41-4.20 means the more preference of using the channel. 4.21-5.00 means the most preference of using the channel. The quality of instrument, reliability and validity, have been examined by 3 expert peers in this field. The IOC (Index of item objective congruence) was 0.874 which was over the standard of 0.5 and alpha coefficient form 30 pretest sample of reliability test was 0.934 which was over the standard of 0.7 (Bunchu & Surachaikunwatana, 2016).

3.4 Data analysis

The study analyzed the data using Descriptive statistics analysis representing mean, standard deviation and inferential statistics analysis. Factor analysis and path analysis have been used. Hypothesis test at confidential level of 95% has been examined by Z-test using SPSS/PC+ AMOS version 19.0 to analyze Structure Equation Modeling (SEM) and investigate concordance of research model with the empirical data. The standard was as follows: P-Value > 0.05, GFI ≥ 0.9, AGFI ≥ 0.9, CFI ≥ 0.9, RMR < 0.1 and RMSEA < 0.1, Chi Square/df < 3 (Kline, 1998).

4. Results

At the beginning of model conformation, researcher has investigated the correlation of independent variables to avoid multicollinearity. Researcher has examined 2 methods as follows:

4.1 Normal distribution: data examination with univariate distribution by considering kurtosis, skewness with the range of ±3.00. Kolmogorov test analyzed the 15 observable variables with interval and ratio scales demonstrated statistics values such as mean (\bar{X}), standard deviation (S.D.), skewness (SK), and kurtosis (KU) as Table 1.

Table 1: Statistics values of 15 observable variables

Channel distribution	Small Sized Enterprises		Medium Sized Enterprises		KU/ SK	t-test
	\bar{X}	S.D.	\bar{X}	S.D.		
Offline channel						
1. Off1	4.51	.604	4.56	.727	-1.235/ .184	-.598
2. Off2	4.61	.660	4.42	0.725	-1.203/ .480	2.681*
3. Off3	4.20	1.000	4.56	.727	- 1.857/2.851	- 3.583*
4. Off4	4.31	.780	4.72	.695	-1.103/ .680	-5.096*

5. Off5	4.80	.493	4.44	.727	-	5.811*
					1.492/1.191	
Offline and online channel						
1. ONOFF1	4.21	.604	4.58	.725	-.484/-	7.346*
					1.297	
2. ONOFF2	4.02	1.000	4.59	.735	-.939/-	6.549*
					-.306	
3. ONOFF3	4.02	.780	4.48	.651	-.887/-	6.550*
					-.746	
4. ONOFF4	4.31	.493	4.59	.721	-.934/-	-5.268*
5. ONOFF5	4.41	.493	4.72	.697	-.884/-	-4.970*
					-.221	
Online channel						
1. ON1	4.61	.489	4.73	.705	-	-
					1.492/1.191	1.904
2. ON2	4.60	.661	4.72	.695	-	-
					1.689/1.298	1.706
3. ON3	4.51	.669	4.56	.727	-1.143/-	-
					.038	0.727
4. ON4	4.50	.675	4.56	.727	-1.003/-	-
					.041	0.783
5. ON5	4.50	.681	4.55	.730	-1.000/-	-
					.043	0.773

From table 1, results of distribution, skewness (SK) and kurtosis (KU), represented that $-1.857 < SK, SU < 2.851$ which relied within the standard range to construct SEM and model's concordance test. A comprehensive comparison of tools for differential analysis between small ($n=235$) and medium ($n=165$) enterprises found that small and medium enterprises tended to use offline channels at statistically significant difference level ($p < 0.05$) in almost factors except the factor that offline allowing quickness in the process (table 1).

According to offline along with online channels, there were significant differences in their opinions towards the usage of all factors between small and medium enterprises at the 0.05 level of significance ($p < 0.05$) (table 1).

In case of online channels, there were significant differences in their opinions towards the usage of all factors between small and medium enterprises at the 0.05 level of significance ($p < 0.05$) (table 1).

4.2 Correlation analysis among observable variables by Kaiser-Meffer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy (KMO) index and Bartlette's test of Sphericity value

The analysis represented the independence of each factor by testing correlation of observable variables as shown in table 2.

Table 2: Results of Correlation analysis among observable variables by KMO index and Bartlette’s test of Sphericity value

Statistics correlation test of variables		Value
Kaiser-Mefer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy: KMO		0.610
Bartlette’s test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-square	5,731.029
	df	55
	Sig.	.000

According to table 2, the standard value is $KMO > 0.6$. KMO analysis in this study represented 0.610 at significance level of 0.000. Then, the analysis indicated that the observable variables were not identity metrics and can be used to analyze the factors in the model.

From the conceptual framework of the research, researcher has reviewed literature and related research along with the application of statistics instrument to scrutinize the suitable variables as shown in figure 2-3. In addition, checking three observed variables were found that variables that cannot be used as a measure of each channel such as the first offline channel was (OFF3) and (OFF5), Offline along with online channels: (ONOFF1) and (ONOFF5), and Online channels: (ON4), and (ON5).

$$\chi^2/df=1.207, df =59, P = 0.949, GFI=0.890, AGFI=0.900, RMSEA= 0.025, RMR = 0.045$$

Figure 2: Structure Equation Modeling of distribution channels influencing credit service adoption by **small enterprises**

$\chi^2/df=2.807$, $df = 84$, $P = 0.449$, $GFI=0.914$, $AGFI=0.908$, $RMSEA= 0.010$, $RMR = 0.015$

Figure 3: Structure Equation Modeling of distribution channels influencing credit service adoption by **medium enterprises**

The results of concordance tests demonstrated that the variables were compatible with the conceptual framework and theory by considering the standard index of SEM as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Comparison of Model Fit Indices used in Structural Equation Modeling under small and medium enterprises

Model-Fit index	Recommended Acceptable Level			small sized enterprises	medium sized enterprises
χ^2/df	0-3	Accepted	<3	1.207	2.807
RMR	0-1	Accepted	<0.05	0.045	0.015
AESMR	0-1	Accepted	<0.05	0.025	0.010
IFG	0-1	Accepted	>0.9	0.890	0.914
IFGA	0-1	Accepted	>0.9	0.900	0.908

From table 3, all Model-Fit index from SEM relied on the determined criteria including the ratio of chi-square and degree of freedom (χ^2/df), goodness of fit index (GFI), adjusted goodness of fit index (AGFI), root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), root mean square residual (RMR).

Table 4: Results of Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis			β	Un.STD	S.E.	P	SMC R-Square
Small Sized Enterprises							
OFF	→	Decision	0.573	0.380	0.043	0.000***	0.757
OFFON	→	Decision	0.392	0.236	0.052	0.006**	0.626
ON	→	Decision	0.531	0.345	0.045	0.000***	0.728
Hypothesis			β	Un.STD	S.E.	P	SMC R-Square
Medium Sized Enterprises							
OFF	→	Decision	0.815	0.420	0.042	0.000***	0.903
OFFON	→	Decision	0.498	0.335	0.034	0.000***	0.705
ON	→	Decision	0.226	0.114	0.011	0.016*	0.475

Note: *** ($p < 0.001$), ** ($p < 0.01$), * ($p < 0.05$)

From table 4, the results of small enterprises indicated that offline channels represented the most influence to credit service adoption with coefficient of determination of 75.7 percent (R square = 0.757) followed by online channels and offline along with online channels with coefficient of determination of 72.8 (R square = 0.728) and 62.6 (R square = 0.626) percent respectively.

Regarding to medium enterprises, the results also showed that offline channels represented the most influence to credit service adoption with coefficient of determination of 90.3 percent (R square = 0.903) followed by offline along with online channels and online channels with coefficient of determination of 70.5 (R square = 0.705) and 47.5 (R square = 0.475) percent respectively.

5. Conclusion, Discussion and Recommendation

5.1 Conclusion and Discussion

The study indicated that P-values were less than 0.05 which mean that the information in the SEM model could explain and concord with the research's conceptual framework. Small and medium enterprises have been proposed as sample groups of the study. The results showed that all Model-Fit index from SEM of small enterprises relied on the determined criteria with 0.64 factor loading (more than 0.40 factor loading's criteria). In case of medium enterprises, all Model-Fit index from SEM also rely on the determined criteria with more than 0.40 factor loading's criteria. Both small and medium enterprises accepted offline channels that influencing credit adoption with coefficient of determination more than 50 percent. Moreover, the study found that

medium enterprises used online channels less than 50 percent with coefficient of determination of 47.5 percent.

5.2 Research Model

The model explained that small enterprises concerned the top 3 most expectation from each channel (Table 1) as follows;

1) Offline channels: small enterprises expected that offline should provide convenient and enough parking lot (mean = 4.80), accessibility (mean = 4.61), and quickness in process (4.51).

2) Offline along with online channels: small enterprises expected that linkage of internet system and the branch should provide accessible and understanding information (mean = 4.41), enough information for service (4.31), and quickness in process (4.21).

3) Online channels: small enterprises expected that these channels should provide quick data search (mean = 4.61), accuracy and precision during data searching (mean = 4.60), and convenient and quick service (mean = 4.51).

According to table 1, there weren't significant difference in online channels between small and medium enterprises at significant level of 0.05. However, there were significant difference in offline along with online channels between small and medium enterprises at significant level of 0.05 which medium enterprises expected the usage of these channels more than small enterprises.

6. Implication

6.1 The dimensions with the greatest contribution

The correlation of distribution channels influencing credit service adoption suggested that offline channels represented the most channels that small enterprises used for credit adoption which could be explained for 75.7%. Offline channels must be supported with convenience, enough parking lot, accessibility and quickness in process. In the same way, medium enterprises preferred offline channels for credit adoption with 90.3% explanation. That emphasized the importance of offline channels in which small and medium enterprises have focused for the main channels for credit adoption. In fact, bank shouldn't cancel the offline channels especially, the branch because of the reduction of the whole transaction in the branch. The analysis of service types in each channel should be considered in order to determine distribution channel strategy.

6.2 Recommendation for the future research

1. Since this research mentioned on business credit for small and medium enterprises, the next study should cover other bank's services such as personal loan, housing loan, and car loan which would widely generate other aspects to bank's channel strategy.

2. The future research should focus on the development of omni-channel which bank industry tends to pursue. Unfortunately, there are some problems and barriers that bank needs to understand and solve before getting to omni-channel.

3. This study concentrates only on small and medium enterprises, according to The Twelfth National Economic and Social Development Plan, other enterprises such as social and community enterprises should be considered to identify appropriated channels for those business.

References

- Angella, K. & Johnson, K. (2016). Power of consumers using social media: Examining the influences of brand-related user-generated content on Facebook. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 58. 98-108.
- Bunchu, K. & Surachaikunwatana, P. (2016). *Factors Affecting Toward Intention Behavior to Use Mobile Banking of Government Saving Bank, Pathumthani 2*. Management, Faculty of Business Administration, University of the Thai Chamber of Commerce.
- Bangkokbiznews. (2015). Retrieved from www.bangkokbiznews.com
- Caruana, A. (2002). Service loyalty: The effects of service quality and the mediating role of customer satisfaction. *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 36 Iss: 7/8, 811-828.
- Harma, A. and Mehrotra, A. (2007). Choosing an optimal channel mix in multichannel environments', *Industrial Marketing Management*, Vol. 36, No. 1, pp. 21-28.
- Jatusripitak, S. (2018), *Drive SMEs into the 4.0 era*. Ministry of Finance.
- Kock, N. & Hadaya, P. (2016). Minimum sample size estimation in PLS-SEM: The inverse square root and gamma-exponential methods: Sample size in PLS-based SEM. *Information Systems Journal*. 28.
- Kline, R. B. (1998). *Methodology in the social sciences. Principles and practice of structural equation modeling*. New York, NY, US: Guilford Press.
- Kotler, P. 2006. *Marketing Management*. 11th Edition. Pearson Education.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. (2009). *Marketing management* (13th ed.). Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Peter, J. P. & Olson, J. C. (2010). *Consumer behavior and marketing strategy* (9th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill Irwin.

-
- Rangaswamy, A. & Bruggen, G. H.V. Opportunities and challenges in multichannel marketing: An introduction to the special issue. *Journal of Interactive Marketing* Volume 19, Issue 2, 2005, Pages 5-11.
- Rattanasuwan, M., & Srijanya, S. (2012). *Creative age marketing*. Bangkok: Tycoon-Brandage Printing. House.
- Revenue Department. (2016). *Characteristics of SMEs*. Retrieved from <http://www.rd.go.th/publish/38056.0.html>.
- Sirimongkol, C. (2011). *Comprehensive product and communication marketing (IMC) factors that Affecting the decision-making behavior of using skin and beauty clinics of female consumers in Bangkok*. Master of Business Administration. Srinakharinwirot University.
- Schiffman, L. G.; & Kanuk, L. L. (2007). *Consumer Behavior*. 9th ed. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice – Hall.
- Tantibunthaweewat, S. & Maneesri, K. (2011). Influence of being part of the job, job satisfaction and Organizational commitment to resignation intention. *Veridian E-Journal*, 6 (3), 699-717.
- Techtarget (2014). *IT channel sales and marketing strategy for the digital era*. Retrieved from <https://searchsalesforce.techtarget.com/definition/multichannel-marketing>.
- Van Dijk, G., Minocha, S. and Laing, A. (2007). Consumers, channels and communication: Online and offline communication in service consumption, *Interacting with Computers*, Vol. 19, No. 1, pp. 7–19.
- Verhoef, P. C., Kannan, P. K. & Inman, J. (2015). From Multi-Channel Retailing to Omni-Channel Retailing: Introduction to the Special Issue on Multi-Channel Retailing: *Journal of Retailing*. 91, 2, p. 174-181.

Online channels for credit application					
1. online providing quick data searching (ON1)					
2. online providing accuracy and precision in data searching (ON2)					
3. online providing convenient and quick service(ON3)					
4. online providing data, rule and procedure searching(ON4)					
5. online providing accessible and convenient channels for credit application (ON5)					

Part 3: The decision for credit service adoption

Please fill ✓ in the box that matched your decision level

- Decision level:**
- 5 refers to the most preferable decision
 - 4 refers to the more preferable decision
 - 3 refers to the medium preferable decision
 - 2 refers to the less preferable decision
 - 1 refers to the least preferable decision

Decision for credit adoption	Decision levels				
	(5)	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)
1. Availability of service process(Decision1)					
2. Quickness within the process of credit application (Decision2)					
3. Standard of bank’s security(Decision3)					